
PROMOTING QUALITY DATA AND CLEANSING TECHNIQUES IN DATA ANALYTICS BASED ON SMART BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

In advancement of recent era, business organization is developing drastically as there is an increase number of Information Technology (IT) as they gives wide impact on the national and international development as they all managing the vast and complex number of data. In order to analyses the performance of data, those vast data has to be processed and analysed. In managing the data, Extract, Transform and Load (DATA) process is applied and stored in the data warehouse as repository in order to take effective distributed based decision as it faces the problem of time consuming process. As the data warehouse takes the data source in the distributed manner as it is difficult to integrate those data. To overcome the above challenges, the Modified DATA based Data warehouse is proposed as it is applied with modified multi-dimensional based bottom up approach as it carried out various activities to deeply analysis the data based on content profiling. In the process of cleaning, confirming and delivery of data depends on the various data sources. Then algorithm makes three various process of data extraction as it provides data cleaning and conforming to create the conform steps based on the source data analysis using data hierarchy structure. Until the data sources gets integrated based on the various distributed database, DATA steps are performed. In the analysis, modified DATA is applied on any real time organization as it takes various source table to compare the actual and expected results. Then various metadata testing is performed on various documentation to makes the process of transformation effective.

Keywords: DATA process, Data extraction, IT organization, Transformation, data warehouse, distributed data

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I. INTRODUCTION

In the CoVID-19 pandemic era, it makes the target on various organization to surviving as these IT business is growing drastically. The business activity is makes various complex survival as it cannot be detached from the IT as it plays a key role in their organizational development [1]. Even though IT organization is growing drastically, it solely depend on the business activity as it gives greater impact. Here big data plays a vital role as the business activity has generated and collected vast amount of data as it needs to be processed and analysed. This big data helps to generate and collect the real time data and the business process is used to perform the large data and determine the resource efficiency, which can be improved and it helps to evaluate the business activity in terms of marketing [2]. The process of big data helps to make the business to run better in terms of optimizing the architecture of data warehouse as it makes the data to more accurate and secure.

Here the data warehouse is the storage repository as it integrates the process of data to be more knowledge as it helps to access the business information and make better decision. This helps to construct the new data warehouse as it integrates the data to be manipulated using Extract Transform Loading (DATA) process [3]. This process of DATA makes the raw data to be analysed and extracted into the storage of data warehouse. This DATA process makes the data to be manipulated from various sources, which includes the improper data elimination, filtering the duplication, data filtering, data cleaning and formatting. The data's considered will be of various formats. The DATA is defined as the process sets as it gets those data from various Online Transaction Processing (OLTP) into data warehouse repository. In DATA initial steps, final data being collected from various heterogeneous data sources as it requires quality data and reliable one. This traditional DATA process requires more execution time as more developed project requires 80% time increase in execution [4]. The data warehouse helps to store the data records as it makes the effective decision process based on the business process in Distributed environment.

Mainly the data warehouse takes the system to perform data extract, data cleaning and deliver to data dimensional from various data sources and able to determine the effective decision making. Then makes data warehouse operates on the source data, presenting the data which depends on various data format [5]. In this research some datasets are considered as it takes academic information along with the faculties and the department. Based on the various departments and faculties who are working will gives which kind of services are offered in the university or institution? Generally, data is arranged and collected in the distributed fashion and initiate the system information [6] and [7]. Then the distributed database is deployed on single or multiple source system.

The advantage of data configuration is to represents the structure organization, autonomy the improved data and their performance; the limitations faced during the configuration is the data standard, complexity and data integrity. The data warehouse process using DATA process is represented in figure 1.

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Figure 1. Data warehouse Process using DATA

In this paper, based on the distributed database, the standard DATA process is more complicated as it does not contain a central mechanism for each database. Based on the data fact of the table, structuring the data help to clean the data with various dimension and then construct the data warehouse based on a certain process. the objective is organized as it gets initiated with the modified multi-dimensional based bottom-up approach as it carried out various activities to deeply analyse the data based on content profiling. The business requirements are provided based on the multi-dimensional representation of the data table. Initially, the particular business process is selected, which is to be modelled and represented as a table and do certain

measurements. Data grain is made to represent the individual representation. Then the data dimension is chosen based on the set of data attributes and identify the numeric facts.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Assessing the performance can be achieved based on the organization's achievement with certain tasks and activities. The organization's achievement and performance can be calculated and analyzed to represent the operational impact, which may be positive or negative [8]. Here comes the role of big data technology as it plays a challenging role while the top companies like Google, Facebook, etc. consider the unstructured data as it needs to be managed and utilized based on vast amount of large data [9]. This big data takes the major role in the field of information technology as it makes the process of managing and analysing the data. As the large volume of data to be process will be much more complex with the standard technologies, big data takes the process of managing and analysing those data [10 - 14]. The information technology purely depends on data utilization and managing them as the entire organization takes the lead as it dependence on the data. Those organization takes the role of organizing the tool to managing the data through application and their features are represented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. CPS Applications

Based on the business organization, data warehouse plays a significant role as it makes the various processes, technologies and tools are performed along with the data as it gathers certain knowledge and useful data as it results in the profitable information based on certain organization activities. In order to utilize the emerging opportunities, there are various integration of data warehouse, mining data, analysing the data in multi dimension with certain

graphical representation [15]. Then these data takes certain analyses to determine the growth and enhancement of the organization. Here the business intelligence includes, data warehouse, data mining, analysis the multi dimension, etc. In this data warehouse technology, data can be managed from various multiple sources as it gives improved insights on the business. It is the repository to store large volumes of information especially as the data gets generated by the business organization. In this data are processed, transformed, and absorbed by the users based on the tools being used by the business organization.

The DATA process is being studied based on the data warehouse on sales as it is represented using pentaho tools [16]. In this study, the sales in the data warehouse are processed to form useful information as it gets analysed and processed to determine the performance of the sales to make effective decision making. [17] has analyzed the data store of the United States from 2014-2017 as it takes the representation of Microsoft office doc as it transforms the data into MYSQL database. The data warehouse is analyzed on certain applications of PHI Minimart using pentaho tools to analyze the data warehouse sales with the help of an DATA system with information sales. The data warehouse is analyzed using OLAP process of data creation as schema. The data sales of minimart sales 2008 [18] as it is represented as sales chart and their total sales for each department in the organization [19].

[20] has consider the online market datasets and based on that the data warehouse is designed and it is represented as the schema of snowflake schema. The data modeling of this snakeflake schema takes various 9 steps of methodology to model the data [21]. The data platform is used to process the data in order to represent the data, which is informative are useful. Business intelligence is applied to determine the effectiveness of decision-making and improved data quality.

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION

Based on the performance of DATA Process, has proposed the DATA process with three process of data changer, cleaning the data and load the data to determine the data robustness. In this work, segment the data and modification are made, which can handle the data to be represented as the data tables among the various users, but those tables are not associated with each other users. Then DATA performance is further modified based on query cache technique as it helps to reduce the response time. Then has modelled the DATA based data warehouse as the managing the organization, data warehouse and users acts an intermediate as here we have considered the dataset of clinical based data warehouse. has consider the development of data warehouse with respect to distributed environment has discussed various DATA process and their approaches being used to determine the effective DATA techniques being selected. The challenges and open issues being addressed is the analyse of the data source in the distributed database and specific data case study must be considered by deploying the modified DATA process in order to analyse the data being used.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the proposed approach, the multi-dimensional model is deployed as it helps to construct the data warehouse as the modeling process takes certain stages as mentioned below,

Figure 3. Data Warehouse Architecture using DATA Process

A. Multi-Dimensional Model:

The data's are modelled based on the process of data warehouse with kimbell's approach as, Initial step helps to identify the business process as analyse the students entry, their registering for the new course, analyse the student grade obtained, student payment and their graduation count of students. Then data can be grained and declared based on the data measure as it is integrated with the data granularity. The data measurement is based on the student information with every year, information of the student who is registering, distribution of grade of the student, graduation data and payment done by the student. The data dimension is identified based on role associated with the student.

“Rajesh (Gender), Semester, Adgami (Religion), Mahesh (Student), Mahesh Reg (Student Registration), Model, Bank Name (Name of the Bank), Delhi (Payment), STAS (High School),”

Finally, the facts are identified based data tables being deployed by the individual user as represented as,

- Student Table | Student Count | Facts
- Table Student Registration | Student Count

Grade table Student | CGPA | GPA

Payment Student Table | Payment Student | Status

B. Modified DATA Process:

In the DATA process, the server, mainframe, source production is taken as the input as it get the initial process of extraction as takes the unstructured data and perform extraction on the data stage and generalize the data as structured one. Then it performs data cleaning as it cleans the unwanted data into useful one. Then data conforms and deliver make the data to be analysed and processed. Finally it is sent back to the use application by the end user as it operates several processes such as, scheduling the data, handling the data exception, data recovery, and data restart, checking the data quality and reliability with certain user support.

Algorithm 1: Modified DATA Process for Data Integration

Input: Server; Mainframe; Data Source

Output: Data Integration

1. Identify the data source to perform data extraction
2. The data tables are structured and their explanation
 - Using a merging strategy, create the master table
 - a. Table 1 □ DB1
 - b. Table 1 □ DB2
 - c. Merger (Table 1 from different DB1 and 2)
 - Using Merge Union Strategy, Create the master table
 - a. Table 1 □ DB1
 - b. Table 1 □ DB2
 - c. Table 1 not influence on Table 2
 - d. Apply Merge strategy with Union Action
 - Using Union Strategy, create a transaction table
 - a. Large table □ Target Table
 - b. Target Table = {Pilot Table}
3. Heterogeneous Data Source
4. DB = DB {Merge and Union Strategy}
5. Perform Data identification and analyze the data source
 - a. hostname (Domain name or IP address of the database server)
 - b. Database name (The schema or other database identifiers)
 - c. Port Username and password to access the data source)
6. IFNULL() and NULL Values Expression
7. Creating the data dimension tables.

The process of data integration is performed and represented in Algorithm 1.

C. Data Cleaning and Conforming:

In the cleaning process, the data errors are detected and removed as inconsistent data's are identified as it results in enhancing the data quality.

- Analysis the data
- Refining the data
- Verify the data

Based on the data rule and value, re-analyze the data based on DATA process to perform data confirmation, data join and association. Then the data helps to create conform data dimension as it takes data hierarchy and dimension

D. Data Delivery and Loading:

In this data table, only user analysis data's are present and for each data table, the key is generated. Here the start schema being used as it helps to de normalize the data and then deliver the data as the targeted data table.

- Slow Changing Dimension (SCD)
- Loading the Fact Table

E. DATA Process Testing:

The main objective of DATA process is to test the data by identifying and collecting the data errors as it occurs before the process of data analytical and reporting. Various data testing are performed i.e. validate the data completion, testing the Meta data and DATA test incrementing. All loaded data are measured as it helps to validate the objective if data completion. The table defined are verified while performing the Meta data testing. Data document can be mapped based on checking the data type, length of the data, checking the data index between the source and destination table. Then the unwanted data duplication can be determined based on the incremented DATA testing.

V. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Based on DATA strategy, data warehouse makes the total cost construction as contains Data Dimension Cost (DDC) and Import Data Cost (IDC).

$$\text{Total Cost (TC)} = \text{Data Dimension Cost (DDC)} + \text{Import Data Cost (IDC)}$$

A. Analysis of the OLAP Process:

As there are two OLAP query requests, various data dimension is required based on value query of fact information as it gets H Base get () operation and Hbase Scan () as represented in Table 1 and 2.

Table 1. Time cost based on Get () operation

No of Rows	HBase	Oracle
1000	4	22
10000	3.6	34
100000	2.8	45

Table 2. Time cost based on Scan () operation

No of Rows	HBase	Oracle
1000	20	25.4
10000	12.5	24.6
100000	19.2	26.6

B. Analysis of DATA process:

Here 1000, 10,000 and 1,00,000 data entries are considered as the HBase and traditional oracle are analysed as represented in Table 3, 4 and 5.

Table 3. DATA Process based on 1000 Datasets (ms)

No of Rows	HBase	Oracle
1	104	34
2	109	16
3	100	15
4	116	12
5	109	13
6	111	25
7	116	12
8	128	13.5
9	120	13.8
10	98	14.2

Table 4. DATA Process based on 10,000 Datasets (ms)

No of Rows	HBase	Oracle
1	650	190
2	600	96
3	625	60
4	680	45
5	800	48
6	790	54
7	765	51
8	600	53
9	605	170
10	790	68

Table 5. DATA Process based on 1,00,000 Datasets (ms)

No of Rows	HBase	Oracle
1	2900	509
2	2850	450
3	2950	465
4	2980	445
5	2450	451
6	2800	458
7	2750	462
8	2950	710
9	3450	462
10	2800	491

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the data heterogeneity problem, DATA process is deployed as it performs certain process such as, data extraction, cleaning the data, data conforming and data delivery & loading. The data content profiling and analysing the data source are performed in the data extraction process. The data's are integrated in the distributed environment as it perform the database with different strategy i.e. merge, merge-union and union. The data conformation is created based on the analysing the data source, data refinement based on structure hierarchy. The data dimension and fact tables are associated in the process of DATA loading. In the analysis, Hbase data warehouse takes reduce time in the process of DATA than the traditional oracle. Ithe HBase takes faster query response by varying the datasets 1000, 10000, 100000 data entries. If the data value is larger, memory consumption is high and the query optimization gets reduced as the data value is smaller and it needs some better data partition in the data value.

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